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EMERGING WIRELESS TECHNOLOGIES IN THE INTERNET OF THINGS : A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things (IoT) incorporates multiple long-range, short-range, and personal area wireless networks and technologies into the designs of IoT applications. This enables numerous business opportunities in fields as diverse as e-health, smart cities, smart homes, among many others. This research analyses some of the major evolving and enabling wireless technologies in the IoT. Particularly, it focuses on ZigBee, 6LoWPAN, Bluetooth Low Energy, LoRa, and the different versions of Wi-Fi including the recent IEEE 802.11ah protocol. The studies evaluate the capabilities and behaviours of these technologies regarding various metrics including the data range and rate, network size, RF Channels and Bandwidth, and power consumption. It is concluded that there is a need to develop a multifaceted technology approach to enable interoperable and secure communications in the IoT.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things, Wireless Technologies, Low-power, M2M Communications.

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DEVICE-TO-DEVICE (D2D) COMMUNICATION UNDER LTE-ADVANCED NETWORKS

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Morocco (D2D) Communication Under LTE-Advanced Networks

ABSTRACT

Device-to-Device (D2D) communication is a new technology that offer many advantages for the LTEadvanced network such us wireless peer-to-peer services and higher spectral efficiency. It is also considered as one of promising techniques for the 5G wireless communications system and used in so many different fields such as network traffic offloading, public safety, social services and applications such as gaming and military applications . The goal of this paper is to present advances on the current 3GPP LTE-advanced system related to Device-to-Device (D2D). In this paper, we provide an overview of the D2D types based on the communication spectrum of D2D transmission, namely Inband D2D communication and Outband D2D communication. Then we present the advantages and disadvantages of each D2D mode. Moreover, architecture and protocol enhancements for D2D communications under LTE-A network are described.

KEYWORDS

D2D;LTE-advanced;Inband D2D;Outband D2D;3GPP;5G.

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INCREASING WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS LIFETIME WITH NEW METHOD

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ABSTRACT

One of the most important issues in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) is severe energy restrictions. As the performance of Sensor Networks is strongly dependence to the network lifetime, researchers seek a way to use node energy supply effectively and increasing network lifetime. As a consequence, it is crucial to use routing algorithms result in decrease energy consumption and better bandwidth utilization. The purpose of this paper is to increase Wireless Sensor Networks lifetime using LEACH-algorithm. So before clustering Network environment, it is divided into two virtual layers (using distance between sensor nodes and base station) and then regarding to sensors position in each of two layers, residual energy of sensor and distance from base station is used in clustering. In this article, we compare proposed algorithm with wellknown LEACH and ELEACH algorithms in homogenous environment (with equal energy for all sensors) and heterogeneous one (energy of half of sensors get doubled), also for static and dynamic situation of base station. Results show that our proposed algorithm delivers improved performance.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), Routing protocols, Clustering in Wireless Sensor Networks .

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AN SDN APPROACH FOR AN ENERGY-EFFICIENT HETEROGENEOUS COMMUNICATION NETWORK IN DISASTER SCENARIOS

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ABSTRACT

Wireless access technologies have been extensively developed aiming to give users the ability to connect to their expected networks anytime, anywhere. This leads to an increment of the number of wireless interfaces integrated into a single mobile device, hence, it allows the device to be able to connect to multiple access networks. However, in some specific cases such as natural disasters, having an uncorrupted and timely information exchanging means is critical for affected victims to survive or to connect to the outside world. This is because the essential network infrastructures in these cases could be destroyed causing a large number of systems to stop working. In that cases, the victims need a heterogeneous communications network in which they can communicate, without a doubt, by using different wireless access technologies, i.e., Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. The network must also be able to smoothly change the access technologies, or called a vertical handover, to ensure QoS for ongoing applications. In addition, the network must have a mechanism to save energy. For these reasons, an SDN approach, which has been proposed in a previous work, is considered. The performance of the system has been validated by a set of experiments in a real testbed. The obtained results show that the proposed vertical handover can save at least 24.42 per cent of the energy consumed by the wireless communication. The handover delay with different UDP traffic is less than 150ms. Moreover, the network allows a device using Bluetooth to talk with another one using Wi-Fi over a heterogeneous connection where the end-to-end jitter is mainly below 20ms and the packet loss rate is as small as 0.2 per cent.

KEYWORDS

Energy-efficient, Vertical handover, Heterogeneous communications network, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Extended SDN controller, Disaster.

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ENERGY-EFFICIENT DATA COLLECTION IN CLUSTERED WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS EMPLOYING DISTRIBUTED DCT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a energy-efficient data collection method is proposed in which an integration between Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) matrix and clustering in wireless sensor networks (WSNs) is exploited. Based on the fact that sensory data in WSNs is often highly correlated and is suitable to be transformed in DCT domain, we propose that each cluster from the networks only sends a small number of large DCT transformed coefficients to the base-station (BS) for data collection in two common ways, either directly or in multi-hop routing. All sensory data from the sensor network can be recovered based on the large coefficients received at the BS. We further analyze and formulate the communication cost as the power consumption for transmitting data in such networks based on stochastic problems. Some common clustering algorithms are applied and compared to verify the analysis and simulation results. Both noise and noiseless environments for the proposed method are considered.

Keywords

Wireless sensor networks, data compression, power consumption, discrete cosine transform

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